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Modeling GRB 221009A's TeV Afterglow with a Relativistic Blast Wave

Project Report

Author: Federico Testagrossa (TH.A.T. Group)

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E-Mail: federico.testagrossa@desy.de

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Abstract

On October 9, 2022 the Fermi and Swift spacecrafts detected a powerful gamma-ray burst, followed by an afterglow which was observed by various observatories over a broad region of the electromagnetic spectrum. The data collected for this event, later dubbed GRB 221009A, revealed that it has been the brightest gamma-ray burst detected so far. In this work we focus on the light curve observed by LHAASO in the very-high energy range $0.3 \text{ TeV} < E_\gamma < 5 \text{ TeV}$. This curve shows a break at $t \sim 20 \text{ s}$, and we model it qualitatively. Our results show that this feature can be explained by a synchrotron-self-compton model when also the effects of the dynamical evolution of the relativistic blast wave that causes the afterglow emission are taken into account.

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Introduction

Gamma-Ray Bursts (GRBs) are the most luminous explosions in the universe, which within seconds release energy comparable to what the Sun releases in its entire lifetime.

These transient events lead to the emission of electromagnetic radiation that can be detected on Earth by satellites and ground-based experiments.

The typical signal of a GRB is composed by two phases: a prompt phase, lasting few seconds and characterized by the emission of low-energy gamma-rays (100 keV – MeV), and a longer afterglow phase, that can last from days to months and can be detected on a broad range of frequencies, from radio to high-energy γ -rays.

The data collected in the last 60 years helped developing different theoretical models. Yet, the puzzling time variability in the prompt phase together with the wide spectrum of features, temporal and energetic, of each event, make the complete understanding of the physics of GRB in both phases a challenging problem.

At present, the most successful explanation to the prompt and afterglow emission has been in the framework of ultra-relativistic jets from the newly born compact objects produced by the collapse of massive stars or the merger of neutron stars and/or stellar mass black holes. This jet undergoes firstly internal dissipations, that would lead to the prompt emission. Then, in their propagation, the ejecta start sweeping and shock-accelerating the external matter surrounding the system, generating the afterglow emission.

During my Summer Student Program at DESY I've worked alongside the Theoretical Astroparticle (THAT) group, studying the dynamics of the ultra-relativistic jet and the consequent afterglow emission. The goal of the project was to analyse in this framework the data collected by the Large High Altitude Air Shower Observatory LHAASO for GRB 221009A, trying to reproduce the qualitative feature of the light curve measured in the Very-High Energy (VHE) range 0.3 TeV – 5 TeV.

After a brief introduction on GRB 221009A and the light curve we want to study, we will proceed in presenting the theoretical framework to model it. First, we will discuss the hydrodynamics of a relativistic blast-wave expanding into a medium; we will derive a differential equation that can account for multiple features in the energetic processes of the blast-wave. Then, we will discuss how the blast-wave dynamics lead to the acceleration of particles, estimating the quantities of interest for the physics and connecting them to the dynamics. Finally, we will adopt a Synchrotron-Self-Compton (SSC) model, accounting for the dynamical evolution of the system, trying to reproduce numerically the observed light curve. The numerical modelling of the particle interactions, transportation and radiative processes is performed using the

1 GRB 221009A

On 9 October 2022 the long gamma-ray burst GRB221009A was detected by the instruments on board of the Fermi and Swift spacecrafts.

The transient event was the brightest GRB ever recorded and scientists started calling it The Brightest Of All Time (BOAT); its fluence was so high to rapidly saturate all the gamma-ray detectors, and later optical observations measured the redshift of the afterglow, $z = 0.151$. From the fluence and the redshift it was possible to estimate an isotropic-equivalent energy release $E_{\gamma,iso} = 1 \times 10^{55}$ erg [1], among the highest measured.

At the time of the trigger the location of this GRB was in the field of view of the Large High Altitude Air Shower Observatory (LHAASO), which in the following hours observed a large flux of VHE photons (100 GeV – 100 TeV). In Figure 1 we show the Energy flux light curve and spectral evolution of the observed afterglow phase integrated over the VHE energy range of 0.3 to 5 TeV. [2].

Figure 1: LHAASO results for the light curve converted to energy flux, integrated over the energy range of 0.3 to 5 TeV. The light curve consists of four segments, that were fitted with a broken power law.

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There are possible explanation to the fast rise phase, but the main explanation for the regions a, b, c, d of the TeV light curve can be the Synchrotron - Self Compton (SSC) emission from relativistic electrons accelerated by external shocks propagating in the material surrounding the explosion.

In this framework, the rise phase before the peak corresponds to the afterglow onset, where the blast wave is free streaming and sweeps an increasing amount of matter, accelerating it. When the blast wave has accelerated a substantial amount of matter it undergoes a relativistic deceleration phase: the transition from the coasting phase to the non-relativistic phase could explain the break in the peak of region b of the Figure. Finally, the break between phases d and e can be explained by a jet break effect.

2 Modelling the early forward shock emission

Afterglow radiation is produced in the interaction between the relativistic jet launched by the progenitor star and the surrounding matter. This interaction creates a forward shock propagating in the circumburst medium (CBM) and a reverse shock propagating into the ejecta. The shocks accelerate particles in the ejecta and in the CBM via diffuse shock acceleration, and the accelerated particles produce the radiation that we observe in the afterglow spectrum. In particular, the synchrotron radiation emitted by the particles in the shocked region is believed to make up the bulk of the low-energy part of the photon spectrum, while inverse Compton emission is commonly employed to explain the high-energy range of the afterglow spectrum, in the so called Synchrotron Self-Compton (SSC) model. Emission from reverse shock acceleration may also be relevant, especially in the low-energy band, but the general interpretation is that most of the detected radiation is emitted by the ambient particles accelerated by the forward shock.

2.1 Blast wave dynamics

To understand the properties of the afterglow spectrum we will first study the hydrodynamical evolution of the fluid region in which the radiation is produced, the blast wave behind the shock front, during the propagation of the forward shock in the surrounding ambient matter.

This can be described by a set of differential equations enforcing the possible ways of exchanging energy between the blast wave and the environment. In the following we will derive such equation [3], accounting for the adiabatic evolution, the shock acceleration of the circumburst material and the radiative energy loss of the blast wave. We will denote quantities measured in the frame comoving with the shocked fluid with primed letters, to distinguish them from quantities measured in the observer frame. This latter is equivalent to the frame of the progenitor star, up to cosmological redshift and the doppler factor given by the motion of the jet, which is different in the two frames.

The energy density of the shocked surrounding medium in the observer frame is given by the $\{00\}$ component of the Energy - Momentum tensor

$$T^{00} = \Gamma^2(\rho'c^2 + e' + p') - p' = \Gamma^2\rho'c^2 + (\hat{\gamma}\Gamma^2 - \hat{\gamma} + 1)e',$$

where $\rho' = n'm_p$ is the comoving mass density, e' is the comoving internal energy density, and p' is the comoving pressure and Γ is the bulk Lorentz factor of the blast wave, through which we transform the comoving expression in the observer frame. In the last expression we wrote the pressure in terms of the adiabatic index $\hat{\gamma} = (4 + \Gamma^{-1})/3$ as $p' = (\hat{\gamma} - 1)e'$.

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Multiplying this energy density by the volume V of the blast wave we obtain the total energy E_{sh} of the shocked region in the observer frame, written in terms of the comoving quantities:

$$E_{\text{sh}} = T^{00}V = T^{00} \frac{V'}{\Gamma} = \Gamma mc^2 + \Gamma_{\text{eff}} U',$$

where $m = \rho' V'$ is the amount of surrounding mass which is swept and shock accelerated to a Lorentz factor Γ , U' is the comoving internal energy and we defined the effective Lorentz factor [4]

$$\Gamma_{\text{eff}} = \frac{\hat{\gamma}\Gamma^2 - \hat{\gamma} + 1}{\Gamma}.$$

In this forward shock model, the total energy E of the blast wave in the observer frame is given by

$$E = E_{\text{ej}} + E_{\text{sh}} = \Gamma(M_0 + m)c^2 + \Gamma_{\text{eff}} U'.$$

A change in total energy E occurs when it's used to accelerate, compress and heat additional mass dm or to radiate part of the internal energy $dU_{\text{rad}} < 0$:

$$dE = d[\Gamma(M_0 + m)c^2 + \Gamma_{\text{eff}} U'] = dmc^2 + \Gamma_{\text{eff}} dU'_{\text{rad}}.$$

The variation of comoving internal energy is given by the sum of three terms:

$$dU' = dU'_{\text{sh}} + dU'_{\text{ad}} + dU'_{\text{rad}}.$$

$dU'_{\text{sh}} = (\Gamma - 1)dmc^2$ is the amount of internal energy that is converted to random kinetic energy of the shocked particles when the shock collides inelastically with an element dm of the CBM, dU'_{rad} is the amount of internal energy radiated by the shock wave and dU'_{ad} is the amount of internal energy converted to work in the adiabatic expansion, that lead to a conversion of thermal energy back to bulk kinetic energy.

Working out the differentials and writing the energy variation in terms of the shock front radius R , the final equation is given by [3]

$$\frac{d\Gamma}{dR} = - \frac{(\Gamma_{\text{eff}+1})(\Gamma - 1)c^2 \frac{dm}{dR} + \Gamma_{\text{eff}} \frac{dU'_{\text{ad}}}{dR}}{(M_0 + m)c^2 + U' \frac{d\Gamma_{\text{eff}}}{d\Gamma}}. \quad (2.1)$$

This equation can be solved (analytically or numerically) once one specifies the geometry of the blast wave, the density profile of ambient matter dm/dR (which is homogeneous for Interstellar Matter (ISM) and assumed to be a power law for winds), the total internal energy U' and the adiabatic loss term dU'_{ad} . Notice that the explicit radiative loss term dU'_{rad} cancels out in the derivation, but radiative contributions are included in the expression for the total internal energy $U' = \int dU'$.

2.2 A simple afterglow model

Having discussed the general equation accounting for the blast wave hydrodynamics, we proceed studying the full dynamics of the afterglow phase in the simplest case: we will

neglect adiabatic and radiative losses and consider a spherical blast wave propagating in an homogeneous medium of number density n .

Assuming $dU'_{ad}/dR = 0$ and considering only the shock contribution in the comoving internal energy $U' = (\Gamma - 1)mc^2$ one can rewrite Eq. 2.1 in the form

$$\frac{d\Gamma}{dm} = -\frac{\hat{\gamma}(\Gamma^2 - 1) - (\hat{\gamma} - 1)(\Gamma - \Gamma^{-1})}{M_0 + m[2\hat{\gamma}\Gamma - (\hat{\gamma} - 1)(1 + \Gamma^{-2})]}, \quad (2.2)$$

that together with the density profile relation

$$\frac{dm}{dR} = 4\pi R^2 n m_p$$

can be solved to get the evolution of the bulk Lorentz factor Γ of the blastwave as function of the shock front radius R .

In Fig. 2 we show the results for $\Gamma(R)$, obtained solving numerically (2.2) using the Euler method. We also compare our solution to the power-law scaling $\Gamma \sim R^{-3/2}$ that can be obtained by simple energy conservation arguments [4], showing their compatibility. Here we assume some benchmark values for a typical CBM density $n = 1 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, which is the density of the Interstellar Matter, the initial ultra-relativistic bulk Lorentz factor of the ejecta $\Gamma_0 = 200$ and the isotropic kinetic energy of the blast wave after prompt emission $E_{k,iso} = 10^{51} \text{ erg}$, from which the ejecta mass can be estimated as $M_0 = E_{k,iso}/(\Gamma_0 c^2)$.

Figure 2: Evolution of the Lorentz factor of the blast wave: the interaction with the ambient matter decelerates the blast wave.

The plot shows clearly the main features of the dynamical evolution of the blast wave in the afterglow phase. Initially, in the coasting phase, the blast wave is so energetic that it streams freely through the CBM. It sweeps up matter and accelerates it, but the energy

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loss is negligible, resulting in a phase with effectively constant Γ . At larger radii the energy given to the external matter becomes comparable with the initial kinetic energy, resulting in a relativistic deceleration phase in which Γ decreases until the matter is at rest.

Being interested in modeling the light curves, we change variables to get the blast wave evolution as function of the comoving time t' and the observer time t . The differential relations between the coordinates are given by [4]:

$$\frac{dt}{dR} = \frac{1 - \beta \cos \theta}{\beta c} \tag{2.3}$$

$$\frac{dt'}{dt} = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1 - \beta \cos \theta)}, \tag{2.4}$$

where θ is the angle between the direction of the ejecta and the direction of the observer from the central engine. In the following we will assume, without loss of generality, $\theta = 0$. In Fig. 3 we show the evolution of Γ and R as function of the observer time t . Our numerical solution is compatible with the semi-analytical solution described in Ref. [5].

Figure 3: Time evolution of the blastwave

We will see that to model the dynamics it will be easier to work in the comoving frame and boost back our results to the frame in which we observe the emitted photons. Thus, it's important to distinguish between t and t' . In Fig. 4 we show the differences between the two times. In particular, we see how they grow at the same rate in the coasting phase, they coincide in the non-relativistic limit, when $\beta = 0$ and $\Gamma = 1$, and the main differences emerge in the deceleration phase.

Figure 4: Comoving and observer time.

2.3 Afterglow dynamics : simulating the spectrum

Having derived how the blast wave evolves during the interaction with the circumburst material, we proceed with the numerical calculation of the afterglow spectrum, accounting for the effects of the dynamics. The simulation is performed by means of AM3, a code that solves numerically the transport equation for each particle species, taking as input a set of parameters describing the system and the interactions and radiative processes assumed to be at work in the system. The standard paradigm to describe most of the afterglow spectra of GRBs is the Synchrotron Self-Compton (SSC). In this model the accelerated electrons emit synchrotron radiation, which in turn becomes the target for the inverse-Compton scattering of the same relativistic electrons that produced it. The inverse-Compton part of the spectrum can reach the VHE region that we want to model (i.e. the TeV spectrum of Fig. 1). For this reason we choose to approach the problem in the simplest way, simulating with AM3 a purely leptonic SSC spectrum. The code requires as input parameters the comoving magnetic field and the injected spectrum of electrons, that we implement as follows.

Comoving magnetic field B'

The intensity of the magnetic field can be estimated assuming that a fraction ϵ_B of the internal energy of the downstream (shocked) medium is converted to magnetic energy density:

$$\frac{B'^2}{8\pi} = \epsilon_B(\Gamma - 1)n_{\text{down}}m_p c^2 = \epsilon_B(\Gamma - 1)4\Gamma^2 n_{\text{up}}m_p c^2 \approx 4\epsilon_B\Gamma^2 n_{\text{up}}m_p c^2,$$

where we used the jumping condition between the downstream (shocked) and upstream (unshocked) densities $n_{\text{down}} = 4\Gamma n_{\text{up}} = 4\Gamma n$.

Solving for B' one gets

$$B' = (32\pi m_p \epsilon_{B\eta})^{1/2} \Gamma c. \quad (2.5)$$

Electron spectrum

We assume that during the expansion of the blast wave a fraction ϵ_e of the comoving power density is injected to the electron population, accelerating them:

$$\frac{dE'_{\text{electron}}}{dt' dV'} = \epsilon_e \frac{nm_p c^3 \Gamma^3}{3R}.$$

We model this flow of energy as the injection of a power-law spectrum of electrons

$$\frac{dN}{dV' dE'} \propto E'^{-p}$$

between two energies E_{\min} and E_{\max} . From shock acceleration theories we expect a spectral index $p \sim 2$; we will assume $p = 2.2$. We estimate the minimum energy E_{\min} of the spectrum as [4]

$$E_{\min} = \gamma_{\min} m_e c^2 = m_e c^2 g(p) \epsilon_e (\Gamma - 1) \frac{m_p}{m_e},$$

where

$$g(p) = \frac{p - 2}{p - 1}.$$

To estimate the maximum energy E_{\max} we use the internal routines of AM3, that computes the maximum attainable energy comparing the acceleration timescale with the cooling timescales, due to synchrotron emission, inverse Compton scattering and adiabatic cooling, defined as in Ref. [5]. We assume an acceleration efficiency parameter $\eta = 0.5$. The timescales will depend on the dynamical state of the system, so they will change with time; we show in Fig. 5 the competition between the different timescales for $t = 500$ s. The figure shows that the maximum energy can be estimated as the intersection of t_{acc} and t_{syn}

Figure 5: Comparison between the timescales of the processes

Simulating the dynamics with AM3

As we've seen the input parameters depend on the dynamical quantities Γ and R . These quantities are not independent, and can be related to the time in the observer frame t_{obs} , that we use as the dynamical parameter. We simulate the dynamics of the system computing the simulation quantities and updating them as AM3 parameters at each timestep of the solver. We stress the fact that this type of modelling depends on a number of free parameters $(n, \epsilon_e, \epsilon_B, \Gamma_0, p, \eta)$ that can be partially estimated from the data, but in general are hard to constrain; a proper statistical analysis should then scan the parameter space, and degeneracies are expected. Here we perform the simulation assuming the best-fit parameter of Ref. [2], with the goal of reproducing qualitatively the light curve. Since we used a simple model and we don't know the parameterisation details of the blast wave, we don't expect to perfectly reproduce it or to get a best-fit of the LHAASO data.

In Fig. 6 the simulated differential number density of electrons and photons are shown for different values of the observer time. The simulation was run with a timestep $dt = 10^{-2} t_{\text{dyn}} = 10^{-2} \frac{R_0}{\Gamma_0 c}$, starting from a time smaller than the one we wanted to study, so that the simulation could converge to the quasi steady state.

Figure 6: Comoving densities: simulation results

2.4 Light curves

With the results shown in plot, we finally compute the energy flux as function of time and compare our light curve to the data.

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From the AM3 results for photons we compute at each timestep the comoving luminosity, L' , as

$$L' = E'_\gamma{}^2 \frac{dN}{dE'_\gamma dt'} = E'_\gamma \left(E'_\gamma \frac{dN}{dE'_\gamma dV'} \right)_{AM3} \frac{V'}{t'_{esc}} .$$

Then we transform to the observer frame by

$$E'_\gamma = \frac{E_\gamma(1+z)}{\Gamma}$$
$$t'_{esc} = \frac{t_{esc}}{\Gamma}$$

and finally we compute the flux as

$$E_\gamma F_E = \Gamma^2 E' \left(E'_\gamma \frac{dN}{dE'_\gamma dV'} \right)_{AM3} \frac{V'}{t'_{esc}} \frac{1}{4\pi d_L^2} , \quad (2.6)$$

where F_E is the number of photons per unit time and unit surface and d_L is the luminosity distance. Here we treat the shell as a point source and don't do the integration over the sphere. In that case the integration would consider the different Doppler factors in the sphere, which could lead to a different result.

In our treatment we approximate the comoving escape time t'_{esc} with the dynamical time

$$t'_{esc} = t'_{dyn} = \frac{R}{\Gamma c}$$

and consider a shell geometry for the blastwave

$$V' = 4\pi R^2 \Delta R = 4\pi \frac{R^3}{9\Gamma} ,$$

where in the last equality we computed the ratio $\Delta R/R\Gamma$ equating the total mass in the shell with a constant mass density times the volume, since the density in the blast wave is constant.

Since experiments collect photons in a finite energy window ΔE_γ , we compare our model to data integrating the simulated F_E over ΔE_γ . In Fig. 7 we show the results of our simulation in the energy range of the light curve of Fig. 1, $\Delta E_\gamma = [0.3 \text{ TeV} - 5 \text{ TeV}]$.

Figure 7: Results of the simulation: comparison to LHAASO data in the VHE range

We see that our model reproduces the qualitative features of the measured light curve, in particular the spectral break at $t \sim 20$ s and the spectral index in the initial part of the decaying phase. We also reproduce the normalization within a factor of a few, but we remark that the parameters used for the simulation are the best-fit ones obtained in the analysis performed by the LHAASO collaboration. Their simulation is different from ours, so we expect that a proper statistical analysis, scanning the parameter space with our numerical model, would increase our agreement with the data. As pointed out in [2], the change in the spectral index at $t \sim 300$ s is due to jet break effects, that we didn't include in our description. To improve our results, a further refinement of our work could implement the jet break and perform a proper statistical analysis of the data.

To give a broader overview of our numerical approach, in Fig. 2.4 we show the results of the multiwavelength modelling of the source, in the keV and in the GeV range.

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Results of the simulation: multiwavelength results

As expected, the intensity of the energy flux is higher for lower energies, and the shape of the curves is similar, since it depends mostly on the dynamics of the blast wave from which the photons are emitted.

3 Conclusions

We presented a numerical treatment of the dynamics of the afterglow phase of a GRB, applying it to the recent data of GRB221009A. We developed that in three steps. First, we studied the dynamical equations governing the evolution of the blastwave during its propagation through the surrounding matter. Here we observed the three phases of the evolution of the blastwave Γ factor: the coasting phase, the relativistic deceleration phase and the non-relativistic phase. Second, we simulated with the AM3 code the particle reactions and the radiative processes involving the material swept by the blastwave. We estimated the relevant parameters as functions of the dynamical variables Γ and R of the blastwave, and updated the input parameters at each timestep of the solver to simulate the effects of the dynamics. Third, and finally, we computed from our numerical results at source the expected light curves at Earth and compared them to the collected multiwavelength data for GRB221009A. We saw that by means of our numerical treatment we were able to reproduce qualitatively the main features of the lightcurve in the VHE range, namely the spectral break due to the transition from the coasting to the relativistic deceleration phase and the power law behavior, with a Synchrotron Self-Compton model. We also observe discrepancies with data, that can be reduced with a more refined analysis. A better overall compatibility can be obtained fitting the lightcurve and finding the most suitable parameter set for our numerical solution. Moreover, the second spectral break in the lightcurve could be modelled including in our treatment the effects of the jet break. We leave this for further work.

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